

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CREATION OF OUTER CLOTHES FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6369511>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 14th March 2022

KEY WORDS

*Nursery, Models,
Casual wear*

ABSTRACT

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Children's clothing has always been created in accordance with the general aesthetic, hygienic, practical requirements for a costume. According to biomedical research, there is a faster maturation of the younger generation.

In those periods when clothes were created according to the principles of falling or loose fitting, children's clothes did not hinder movement, did not squeeze the internal organs, they contributed to the life and development of the child.

Children's clothing is diverse and includes many products. There are more clothes for children than for adults. Children's clothing is designed for girls, boys, for both sexes. The size is usually determined by the height of the baby, his age.

In the modern dimensional typology of the child population, six age groups are distinguished:

- infant (up to one year);

- Nursery (from one year to three years);
- preschool (from 3 years to 7 years);
- junior school (from 7 years to 11.5 years);
- senior school (from 11.5 years to 14.5 years);
- adolescent (from 14.5 years to 18 years).

For kids, there should not be things with narrow collars, tight elastic bands and small buttons. Underwear should be cotton or linen. They breathe and absorb moisture. It is used for the manufacture of children's underwear and cotton knitwear. The material is elastic, does not stretch and does not shrink when washed [1].

Models for babies usually have fasteners, ties, so that the clothes are well fixed and convenient to put on and take off. The main items of clothing for preschool and school children: dresses, sweaters, skirts, sundresses, t-shirts, shirts, suits, jackets,

jackets, trousers, shorts, jacket, coat and many other things.

They create kits for various purposes. The sets include the same types of clothing, but differ in design, materials and design. According to the intended purpose, children's clothing is divided into: home, casual, solemn, sports.

Casual wear - comfortable and hardwearing in a business style with a moderate amount of decor. Formal wear - classic style, romantic, folk or fantasy. Home and sportswear should be comfortable and hygienic.

Children of the teenage and youth groups are often referred to as teenagers. The clothes of children in these two age groups are different from other children's clothes. It often traces some elements of adult fashion and, at the same time, reflects the current styles of youth subcultures. This factor requires a special approach to the process of artistic design of clothes for teenagers.

Children's clothing of the first three age groups is basically stable. Its development is logical to a certain extent, which is dictated by its main purpose - to provide utilitarian and aesthetic comfort for the child's normal life.

At the same time, utility implies coordination solely with the practical use of clothing, that is, its functional purpose. The basic law that operates in the modeling of all types of children's clothing is the dependence of the shape and silhouette of clothing on age-related physique. The most important factors in determining the silhouette, shape and length of children's clothing are the ratio of the length of the torso, arms and legs and the degree of natural waistline revealed depending on the height. In addition to the age

characteristics of the physique of children, the nature of children's clothing is also determined by other factors - climatic conditions, the influence of fashion, and also, in recent times, the social group that is targeted at the production and sale of clothing for children. When designing children's clothing, it should be remembered that clothing, like everything that surrounds a child, actively affects his psyche, therefore, it performs a socially significant educational function [2].

Designing children's clothing is impossible without taking into account climatic conditions. So, clothes of northern latitudes require significant insulation (batting, padding polyester, fur or other modern insulating materials) and a multi-layered internal solution. In temperate climates, versatile outerwear is required that can be transformed by attaching additional insulating pads, capes and hoods that protect against cold and precipitation. In warm climates, children's clothing needs protection from the scorching sun and hot, dry winds. The difference between the microclimate in the city and the countryside within the same climatic zone should also be taken into account. In all cases, the best way to organize children's clothing is to layer and transform.

The influence of fashion on children's clothing in general is not as significant as on adult clothing. The exception is clothing for teenagers. However, fashion, of course, affects children's clothing to one degree or another, and this can be traced by considering the change in the forms of children's clothing during the late 20th and early 21st centuries.

Designing children's clothing in an industrial production environment involves taking into account the following

requirements for children's clothing, the main of which are:

- beauty,
- convenience,
- hygiene,
- security,
- taking into account the peculiarities of the physiological and psychological development of the child at each age.

All these requirements are reduced to a complex of modern requirements of a utilitarian-practical, hygienic and artistic order [3].

The utilitarian and practical requirements for children's clothing are their usefulness, convenience, practicality, that is, expediency and economy. Given that clothing should protect the child from both heat and cold, from rain and wind, a wide variety of types of clothing is provided in terms of assortment, shapes, materials, and colors. Given the speed with which children (especially at a younger age) grow out of clothes, it is recommended to use inexpensive fabrics and finishing materials for their manufacture. An exception is clothes intended for special occasions, as well as clothes aimed at a circle of consumers with a high income and a level of financial security. The high mobility of children requires strength from clothes, which is ensured, on the one hand, by the wear resistance of the fabric to abrasion, fading, washing, cleaning and wet-heat treatment, on the other hand, by the correct design and precise technological manufacture of the product.

Hygienic requirements for children's clothing determine the choice of materials depending on the specific purpose of the product and climatic conditions, as well as the optimization of the package of materials and product design. Children's

clothing is made from various materials: fabrics, knitwear, artificial or natural fur, film materials, artificial and natural suede and leather. General requirements for them: minimum weight, pleasant feeling to the touch, no harmful effects on the body. The leading materials are fabrics and knitwear, which are successfully used in the manufacture of all types of children's clothing. Hygiene requirements are best met by knitwear and cotton fabrics: they are breathable, hygroscopic, thermally conductive and light. The linen range of children's clothing is made from materials that are hygroscopic, air and vapor permeable, light and soft. Cotton and viscose materials are best suited for children's underwear.

Materials for the dress assortment can be either somewhat loose, soft and have good air and vapor permeability, or they can be more dense, but thin and soft. For summer children's clothing, cotton and linen fabrics, as well as thin knitted fabrics, are most often used. For winter clothes of the dress group - plaid, velveteen, cashmere, dense knitted fabrics, light and loose woolen and half-woolen fabrics. Materials for outerwear that protects a child from precipitation should be water-repellent, dense, and light. Raincoat materials are most suitable for this range of clothing [4].

Fabrics for insulated outerwear (coats, jackets) should be soft, light, fairly dense; often two-layer materials are used with a fleece inside, which creates a good heat-insulating air layer. Certain requirements are imposed on the shape and cut of children's clothing. First of all, nothing in the design should interfere with the child, irritate him, impede freedom of movement, breathing, blood circulation. All sorts of tight belts and elastic bands that tighten

the body, high tight collars that support the neck and interfere with normal blood circulation are not recommended. Clothing should be light and should rest primarily on the shoulders.

An important condition for the comfort and safety of children's clothing is its layering, especially in winter clothing, as it contributes to a slower and more uniform loss of heat from the body surface. Aesthetic requirements are also imposed on children's clothing, implying the beauty of the color and pattern of materials, the novelty and elegance of the compositional solution, corresponding to the age and physique of the child; sty left unity in the solution of individual items, from which you can make a harmonious set and a whole ensemble of clothes.

The aesthetic requirements for children's clothing are met by materials of bright, saturated or delicate color tones. The color of the materials of children's clothing should be pure and delicate shades. The most common in the range of children's clothing are materials in which the pattern and field are in contrasting color combinations, which is explained by the desire of children (especially younger children) for contrasting, bright colors, since a sonorous, colorful combination is remembered by them faster. However, one should not forget that too bright, saturated tones, such as orange and bright red, have a negative, exciting effect on the child's psyche, so they should be used in small quantities, using in coquettes, collars, cuffs, hats and mittens, appliques, etc [5].

The choice of fabric pattern - its content, rhythm, scale and fullness of the canvas - depends on the age of the child, the characteristics of his physique, appearance and mental development. After all, each age

is characterized by a certain perception of the surrounding world of things, animals and plants. The drawing not only serves as a beautiful design of the fabric, but also carries an educational burden, helps the child in understanding reality, and also instills a taste for beauty. Widely used fabrics with a classic pattern of peas, stripes, cells, floral ornaments. However, the nature of the floral ornament should be simple, understandable to the child, so that the child would have a desire to examine it, to find the same motive in nature [3].

Of interest are fabrics with a thematic pattern, the motifs of which are taken from the objects around the child, well-known objects, songs, fairy tales, and poems. Children like them, awaken their curiosity, stimulate the child's imagination and even the desire to portray fairy tale characters, imitate representatives of professions understandable to children, etc. The size of the pattern on the fabric should be small, proportional to the size of the product and the entire child's figure, since too large a drawing can visually distort the figure. The simplicity and clarity of the pattern on the fabric should be emphasized and reinforced by its clear rhythmic construction. The rhythmic repetition of the pattern on the fabric contributes to fixing its image in the memory of the child. Drawings, especially thematic ones, should not densely fill the background of the fabric, otherwise it will be difficult for the child to perceive it.

The constructive and compositional solution of children's clothing has its own characteristics that distinguish it from how clothing for adults is created. First of all, you should pay attention to the ratio of individual parts of clothing to each other and all clothing with a child's figure. The

main role in the proportioning of the product is assigned to the length, since it is with the help of the length of the product that one can give the figure visual proportionality, that is, the most harmonious ratio between the sizes of the torso, head, legs and arms, make the child more slender, and the figure more elongated. In children's clothing, the length is relatively constant and is determined according to the age group. The length of girls' dresses and boys' trousers is determined by the proportions of the figure, characteristic of each age group. It should be remembered that an excessive increase in the length of the dress or trousers will lead to visual weighting of the torso and shortening of the legs.

The length of clothes of teenagers and senior schoolchildren is increasing and is already largely dependent on fashion. For the organization of the proportional articulation of the child's figure, the upper part of the bodice - the yoke - is of great importance. In children's clothing, it can have a variety of configurations and sizes and suggest appropriate silhouette solutions. In children's clothing, the coquette is a constructive and sometimes decorative detail. As a constructive element, it creates the necessary volume of the form; gathers, tucks, folds, necessary for shaping, extend from its lower edge. Often the yoke is finished with embroidery, applique, stitching, sometimes it is made from materials of different colors and textures. An invariable requirement of any kind of children's clothing is a simple and clear form of the collar. The degree of fit of the collar to the neck, its cut, size and shape depend on the age characteristics of the physique. In the clothes of children of younger age groups with a short neck, flat-

lying collars, without a stand, separated from the neck, are more often used. Large under-cut sailor-type collars go well with children's dresses of all ages: in babies, such a collar corresponds to the size of the head, expands narrow shoulders and visually changes the ratio of the horizontal and vertical axes of the figure; large collars give a special elegance to the dress of middle-aged and older children.

With age, the neck of the child lengthens and, accordingly, the degree of fit of the collar to it and its height increase in clothes, and the dimensions may decrease. Decorative detachable collars are interesting in children's clothing, they can significantly change the look of the same dress. So, a large lace collar gives solemnity and elegance to clothes, and a small modest collar - composure and neatness.

The shape of the sleeves in children's clothing changes with a change in the proportions of the figure [4].

Long sleeves are not made narrow, as narrow sleeves, tightly fitting the arms, are uncomfortable for children and make it difficult to move. The exception is sportswear made of knitted fabrics. Long sleeves of any design (set-in, one-piece, raglan) are most often decorated with cuffs in the form of a straight bar, forming a small lap. As the arm grows and lengthens, the sleeve falls due to this overlap.

In the design of children's clothing, great attention should be paid to finishing. Finishing can be: hand and machine knitting, lace, applique, braid, cord, fringe, soutache, line, knitwear, leather, fur. Decorative design of clothes can be carried out with the help of piping, frills, flounces, pleats, pleats. The nature of the decoration, its quantity, themes and techniques of technical implementation depend on the

age of the child. Trimming is especially widely used in the clothes of children of nursery and preschool groups, in the form of thematic applications or embroideries. In the clothes of school-age children, decorative stitches, colored inlays, patterned braid, vertically and horizontally stitched folds and tucks, frills serve as decorations. and frills, as well as embroidery and applique. Outerwear is trimmed with leather, velvet, cord,

soutache, braid, fur, stitch. When applying finishing, one should, of course, observe the measure, coordinating the amount of finishing with the proportions of clothing, the purpose of clothing and the nature of its surface [5].

Thus, clothing should reflect age-related changes, the formation of new psychological mechanisms of activity and behavior of children.

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